

Internal Controls system and Corruption in Ethiopia selected Higher Institutions

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine how internal control mechanisms relate to the prevalence of corruption within universities. To attain the objectives, two hundred twelve (212) personnel from essential sectors, including anti-corruption, internal audit, procurement, and finance, were selected by probability sampling. Survey data was collected as the primary source of information, focusing on ten universities in the southern region. The study utilized descriptive methods to assess the current internal control systems and explanatory approaches, specifically regression analysis, to ascertain the type and strength of the relationship between these systems and corruption levels, resulting in findings. A key discovery was a disconnect between the documented existence of institutional policies and internal control procedures and their actual implementation within the daily operations of the universities. Notably, the statistical findings from the regression analysis indicated a significant inverse correlation, suggesting that stronger internal control systems are associated with lower levels of corruption. The findings recommend that the university administrations should prioritize the effective implementation of comprehensive internal control systems. Furthermore, it stresses the need for institutions to conduct thorough assessments of their current corruption vulnerabilities and strategically focus their efforts and resources on strengthening controls in the areas most susceptible to unethical practices. This proactive approach is essential for fostering greater transparency and accountability within the university environment.

Key words: Control, Corruption, Risk assessment, corruption index

Introduction

Corruption has been a persistent issue throughout history, evolving over the years into a multifaceted phenomenon. And its investigation is a challenging issue. It imposes harm upon a nation's commercial activities and economic stability (Unggul & Prakasa, 2024). It is the abuse of public office for personal advantage, particularly the employment of an official position, title, or prestige. Corrupt conduct encompasses bribery, extortion, fraud, embezzlement, nepotism, cronyism, misappropriation of public assets and property for personal gain, and influence peddling(Myint, 2000).

Corruption generally exerts a broad spectrum of detrimental impacts on societal productivity and governmental legitimacy. It constrains investment and growth, resulting in ineffective governance. Developing nations and those transitioning from socialism are especially vulnerable. However, corruption is a global issue (Susan Rose-Ackerman, 2016) that negatively impacts economic growth and development (Malagueño et al., 2010). The term “corruption” refers to the abuse of power in the public sector for private benefit. Many developing nations face this issue due to ineffective law enforcement and a general lack of knowledge about good governance. It lowers investment in public services and infrastructure, which impacts economic growth(Umar et al., 2021).

“Internal controls” denotes a set of policies, procedures, and practices designed to prevent, detect, and address faults, errors, and anomalies. Internal control systems can help mitigate corruption(Batts, 2022). The rent-seeking theory claims that power is the principal motive for fraud. It is an abuse of power by the company's management to further its interests. Internal control is a management tool that helps prevent corruption and is an important part of corporate governance(Wang et al., 2022). The ICS contributes to achieving the firm's objectives and mission by reducing risks linked to the changing social, political, and economic landscape, plus the potential unreliability of the operational systems that execute management's daily strategies(Roberta Provasi & Patrizia Riva, 2015).

Internal control systems play an important role in preventing and detecting fraudulent actions. Institutions implement robust and efficient internal control policies and processes to prevent and

identify fraud (Ndege Joseph et al., 2015; Yuniarti, 2017), help to reduce financial corruption (Sherien and Sayed, 2023). The lack of sufficient internal controls contributes positively to the prevalence of corruption (Muhtar et al., 2023). Various studies assert that internal control can significantly contribute to fraud prevention in governmental and non-governmental organizations (Abiola & Oyewole, 2013; Agyeman, 2016; Haladu, 2018; Hasnawati & Amin, 2020; RASHID, 2022; Shaki et al., 2021; Taufik, 2019; Ubesie et al., 2023; Widilestariningtyas et al., 2016). The internal control system prevents corruption (Hendri et al., 2020), enhances performances (Cavaliere et al., 2021), prevent accounting fraud tendency (Fernandhytia & Muslichah, 2020) and corruption (Nasruddin et al., 2023).

Corruption in the public sector of Ethiopia is escalating significantly. Entities entrusted with responsibility engage in corruption methodically and systematically. The anti-corruption legislation is ineffective in curbing the problem. It significantly impacts socio-economic development and governance (Degye Gashu, 2024).

The report from the Office of Federal Audit General of Ethiopia reveals alarming figures: 14.11 billion birrs in receivable accounts, with nearly 11 billion birrs overdue by a decade; 363 million birrs in unjustified expenditures; 514.5 million birrs that were not promptly reconciled; and 19.4 billion birrs in uncollected revenue from entities that make money. The company neglected to document self-generated and uncollected revenues in income ledgers, collected revenues without an authorized tariff schedule, and procured goods and services in violation of applicable laws, regulations, and procedures. In addition to confirming the presence of financial misconduct, there is evidence of misuse of government assets and government-funded building projects plagued by cost overruns and delays or that have been entirely halted. These findings indicate substantial control weaknesses in the public sector, resulting in corruption (OFAG, 2024). There is still a significant amount of fraud in sub-Saharan African countries. In 2024, two-thirds of the world's 180 nations had corruption perception index (CPI) scores below 50, according to Transparency International's annual report on the index. These findings demonstrated that corruption is rampant in several nations around the globe. A country is free of corruption if its score is 100. In 2023, Ethiopia placed 99th out of all countries with a score below 50. The country's score was 37. The CPI score is unchanged from 2023, but the rank has grown from 98 to 99.

In Ethiopia, the Public suffer from a deficient internal control system and elevated levels of corruption. Consequently, the current research aims to tackle the issue by evaluating the efficacy of internal control in mitigating corruption.

Objectives

The general objective of the study is to investigate the relationship between internal control system effectiveness and corruption prevention

Specific Objectives

- To investigate the existing internal control system effectiveness to prevent corruption
- To examine the effects of Internal control systems on Corruption.

Literature Review

Internal control

The COSO Framework helps entities assess how well their internal control systems perform in achieving management-defined objectives. The first goal is operational(Figure1). It deals with how well the company does its day-to-day business including meeting financial and operational performance goals and keeping assets safe from harm. The second is reporting objectives, which include trustworthy, on-time, open, and other requirements set by regulators, standard-setters, or the organization's rules for internal and external financial and non-financial reporting to stakeholders. The last is compliance objectives, which relate to the company's obligation to adhere to applicable laws and regulations(COSO, 2013).

Fig 1. COSO frame

Corruption Level in Ethiopia

Corruption in the public sector exhibits considerable regional variation globally (Figure 2). Western Europe was the region least affected by public sector corruption. The most corrupt regions are Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), followed by East and Central Asia, and the Middle East and North Africa (MENA). No substantial variation has occurred in the global average of public sector corruption year round. Ethiopia, somewhat surpassing the SSA average, demonstrated steady progress in mitigating public sector corruption until 2021. There has been a swift escalation in public-sector corruption within the past three years (2021–2023). Since 2019, domestic tensions and political violence have proliferated, creating a conducive climate for unethical behaviors.

Fig2. Source: Adopted from Degye Goshu, Arega Shume & Demirew Getachew(2024)

Transparency International reports that the corruption level in Ethiopia is exceedingly high. Ethiopia's CPI rank starts at 102 in 2015, rises to 114 in 2018, declines to 87 in 2021, and ultimately rises to 99 in 2024. In 2015, the CPI stood at 33 out of 100, gradually increased to 39 in 2021 and slightly decreased to 37 in 2024. The data indicates that Ethiopia's CPI ranges from 33 to 39, below the average (Figure 3).

Fig 3. Level of corruption in Ethiopia

Corruption in Education Sector

Corruption in education shows up in different ways, such as mismanagement of resources, serious fraud in purchasing, and small benefits from petty corruption and unclear financial practices. Corruption manifests in multiple ways, including but not limited to clientelism, rent-seeking, and state capture. Although anti-corruption rules are robust in theory, their implementation is insufficient (Rahman, 2018).

The situation's complexity has resulted in a limited understanding of the extent and nature of corruption within Ethiopia's education sector. The manifestations of corruption within the education sector are collusion among departments to circumvent the procurement process, favouritism, nepotism, or bribery in the chosen of suppliers, and evasion of established procurement protocols, and specifications tailored to benefit a particular supplier. Fraud and the falsification of tender documents, whether or not accompanied by bribery, constitute collusion among contractors or consultants during the bidding process. Bribery is used to influence the evaluation of tender awards and related matters (Burns & Dalrymple, 2012).

Methodology

The study employed a mixed-methods research methodology. A questionnaire was administered to gather primary data from the internal audit section. The survey respondents included finance professionals, procurement specialists, internal auditors, and anti-corruption experts. The total population was 454. The sample size was determined using the Yamane Formula, resulting in the selection of 212 respondents through a proportional system. A simple linear regression model was employed, and the data were analyzed using SPSS.

Sample size determination

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where,

n= sample size

N= the total size of population

e= acceptable sampling error, 95% confidence level

454

$$(1+454(0.05^2))$$

Sample size = **212**

Variables measurement

This study looked at the independent variable, which is how strong and effective the internal control system is, and the dependent variable, the level of corruption, by asking people for their opinions using a standard five-point Likert scale questionnaire. This method enabled us to measure the extent of participants' agreement or disagreement with statements on these ideas.

The internal control system was assessed based on the implementation and efficacy of the five fundamental components delineated in the COSO (Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission) framework. The questionnaires included items aimed at eliciting respondents' subjective evaluations of the frequency of certain corrupt activities inside the institution.

Model

$$\text{Cor} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{ICS} + \epsilon$$

Where Cor = Level of Corruption (the dependent variable)

ICS = Strength/Effectiveness of the Internal Control System (the independent variable)

β_0 = Intercept (the expected level of corruption when ICS is zero)

β_1 = Coefficient for ICS (representing the change in corruption for a one-unit change in ICS)

ϵ = Error term (capturing other factors influencing corruption and random variation)

Table 1 Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha
.790

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the survey instrument, as indicated in Table 1, was 0.790. This outcome is within the acceptable range, indicating that the instrument demonstrates a good level of validity and reliability.

Descriptive statistics to assess the internal audit effectiveness to prevent corruption

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics				
Description	M in i	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Control Environment				
The organizational structure clearly defines roles, responsibilities, and lines of authority to prevent conflicts of interest.	1	5	4.13	.94719
There is a clear and accessible code of conduct that explicitly prohibits corrupt practices.	1	5	2.67	1.45750
All the policies and systems functioning well	1	3	1.70	.80885
Average	2.83			
Risk Assessment				
The organization regularly identifies and assesses the specific corruption risks it faces.	1	5.00	2.81	1.11221
The organization has established clear risk tolerance levels for corruption.	1	5.00	2.32	1.21421
The risk assessment process is updated regularly to reflect changes in the organization's environment and operations	1	3.00	1.43	.74485
Average mean	2.19			
Control Activities				
Authorization and approval processes are clearly defined and consistently applied.	1	5	3.27	1.94733
There are adequate physical controls over sensitive assets and information.	1	5	2.21	1.60604
Transaction processing and record-keeping are accurate, complete, and timely.	1	5	2.61	1.42724
There are specific controls in place for high-risk areas such as procurement, contracting, and interactions with external parties.	1	5	2.91	1.63947
Average	2.75			

Information Communication				
Relevant information about anti-corruption policies and procedures is effectively communicated to all employees.	1	5	2.08	1.40570
Employees are aware of how to report suspected instances of corruption.	1	5	2.01	1.58907
There is open communication and feedback between management and employees regarding ethical concerns.	1	3	2.00	.75913
Average	2.03			
Monitoring				
Management regularly monitors the effectiveness of anti-corruption controls.	1	5	3.23	1.33234
Internal audit independently evaluates the design and operating effectiveness of anti-corruption controls.	1	4	2.13	1.04908
Findings from monitoring activities are promptly addressed and lead to corrective actions.	1	5	3.50	1.34668
Average	2.95			
Grand Average Mean	2.55			

As of (Al-Sayaada & et .al, 2006), a mean score between 1.00 and 2.60 indicates disagreement, a mean score between 2.60 and 3.40 reflects neutrality, and a mean score above 3.40 signifies agreement. Therefore, the overall mean score of 2.55 indicates that the internal control system is ineffective in combating corruption within the chosen public universities in Ethiopia.

The comprehensive findings reveal that the participants agreed organizations established internal control policies and procedures, as evidenced by a mean score of 4.3.

However, there was disagreement concerning the effectiveness of the existing policies, which received a mean score of 1.7. The mean scores for the control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring were 2.83, 2.19, 2.75, 2.03, and 2.95, respectively, indicating public universities have a weak internal control system.

Regression analysis

Table 3 Model Summary										
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					DW
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	-.707 ^a	.500	.497	.71525	.500	197.71	1	198	.000	1.733
a. Predictors: (Constant), ICS										
b. Dependent Variable: Cor										

The value of 'r' at -0.707 signifies a robust negative linear correlation between the predictor and the dependent variable (Cor), which means that as IC rises, Cor often declines, and conversely. R Square (0.500) indicates that IC elucidates 50% of the variance in Cor. The significance F change of 0.000 indicates that "IC" is a statistically significant predictor of the dependent variable (DV). Typically, the model demonstrates statistical significance, with the independent variable explaining 50% of the variance in the dependent variable (Table 3).

Table 4 ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	101.144	1	101.144	197.710	.000 ^b
	Residual	101.293	210	.512		
	Total	202.437	211			
a. Dependent Variable: Cor						
b. Predictors: (Constant), ICS						

The data in the table show that ICS is a strong predictor of Co, with a "Sig." value of 0.000 and an F-statistic of 197.710. The model accounts for a significant portion of the unexplained differences in Cor, as indicated by the much larger Mean Square Regression (101.144) compared to the Mean Square Residual (0.512). Therefore, there is statistical significance in the regression model, as seen in the ANOVA table.

Table 5 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.371	.182		7.543	.000
	ICS	-.652	.046	-.707	-14.061	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Cor

The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) of -0.652 signifies that for each one-point increase in the Internal Control System score, the perceived level of corruption score is likely to decrease by 0.652 points.

The regression analysis indicates a statistically significant inverse link between internal control and corruption. As internal control mechanisms enhance, corruption levels are anticipated to diminish. The p-value 0.000 demonstrates the statistical significance of the results, affirming that this association is not attributable to chance. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

This finding aligns with the work of (Muhtar et al., 2023), who discovered that weaknesses in the internal control system have a positive correlation with corruption. The correlation between the internal control system and corruption is negative.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The investigation concluded that the internal control systems in the examined area are deficient. The internal control system adversely impacts corruption, indicating a considerable negative influence. The inadequacy of internal control indicates significant corruption.

The study recommended that the institutions enact "sunshine laws" for pertinent information, increase whistleblower protection, and ensure independent organizations can investigate and prosecute corruption cases connected to internal control shortcomings. Implement policies that increase openness in organizational operations, financial reporting, and decision-making processes. Strengthen accountability measures for failures in internal control that lead to

corruption and allocate resources for training and capacity-building programs focusing on internal control implementation and anti-corruption measures for personnel at all levels within relevant organizations. Policymakers must prioritize the development and enhancement of mechanisms to strengthen the internal control system. And reform anti-corruption policy and enforcement mechanisms.

Limitation of the study

Selected public universities were the primary focus of the investigation. The results may not be generalizable to other universities because of differences in size, technology, organizational culture, funding strategies, and governance structures.

Further study

The research concentrated exclusively on a single public university. It is advisable to conduct further research on comparative studies involving private universities. A more detailed analysis is required to examine the human element in internal control and corruption, focusing on factors such as ethical culture, awareness, and individuals' willingness to circumvent controls.

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